

Improving remote tactile interaction: integrating force-based localization to control artificial touch on the forearm with haptic feedback

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Abstract. This paper presents a novel approach that aims to improve remote tactile interaction by integrating force-based localization to control artificial touch sensations on the forearm. This work focuses on a touch-sensitive plate that serves as an input interface and enables force-based localization processes while being equipped with haptic feedback features such as tactile vibrations and auditory cues. At the same time, a gantry robotic system serves as an output mechanism that enables precise modulation of artificial touch sensations on the forearm in response to inputs from the touch-sensitive plate. This integration aims to bridge the gap between physical presence and remote tactile interaction, enhancing immersion and usability for the user, and allows users to interact with the system remotely.

Keywords: artificial touch control · force based localization · tactile interaction · haptic feedback

1 Introduction

In recent years, technological advances have paved the way for innovative solutions aimed at improving human-machine interaction, particularly in the area of tactile interaction. Tactile interaction [1], an essential aspect of the human-robot engagement, remains a complex challenge in robotics, where users can experience and manipulate tactile sensations from a distance. Future Affair [2] is an interdisciplinary project that combines art, science and technology to explore the meaning of alternatives to interpersonal touch. This artistic-scientific project aims to address current societal challenges such as the lack of touch, loneliness and separation due to the increasing integration of technology into our daily routines [3].

This paper presents a control approach that integrates a gantry robotic system [4] and a touch-sensitive plate to remotely control artificial touch on the forearm by a 3D-printed finger. For input, the force-based localization technique

is used together with Google Mediapipe and OpenCV. This approach provides precise control and manipulation of tactile interaction through haptic feedback.

2 Control Approach

The main control approach of the system contains different subsystems, called touching system and touched system (Fig. 1). The challenge here was the difference in the size of the hands and the question of how to control the different stiffness of the hands. The control approach should be therefore adaptable to the different hands. The operation of the system starts with an idle state in which it is ensured that the finger module carriage is aligned at the home position $[0,0]$ to avoid interference with the camera. The localization algorithm is then activated and waits for the operator to place their arm within the defined working area. As soon as the arm has been detected and the operator has given his consent via the consent switch, the system enters the super state.

Fig. 1. General touching system (left) and touched system (right)

This super state checks the presence of the force reference to ensure that the touch movement is only triggered at the exact point. Any change to the position or force reference puts the system into the combined movement and touch state, with both algorithms being executed simultaneously. If the force reference is missed, the system switches to the force reset state and prompts the finger to return to its rest position to prevent over extension. The system then returns to the basic state of movement. With the touched system, a beep sound serves as feedback until the consent button is activated by the touching system to signal the operator's readiness. Once activated, the beep sound stops, allowing the operator to freely navigate the touch-sensitive plate while applying force to simulate a touch on the forearm. At the same time, the feedback from the touching system is transmitted to the touched system via a potentiometer. Lower vibrations show that the person is willing to be touched on the left side, and higher vibrations signify a preference for the right side. In addition, remote communication via HiveMQ cloud provider is optimized with the MQTT protocol for faster response times.

3 Experiments and Conclusion

In order to verify whether the artificial touch and haptic feedback was achieved precisely, some experiments were conducted as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2. Touched system Vs. touching system co-ordinates results

In the experiments, participants interacted with the touch-sensitive plate and gauging their tactile sensations during the remote interaction. A series of controlled tests were designed to evaluate the effectiveness of the force-based localization processes in generating tactile feedback on the forearm. Participants assessed their subjective experience and perception of the haptic feedback from the plate. The data collected from these experiments provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the integrated system in replicating tactile sensations from a distance and enhancing the user's sensory experience. Results showed a high similarity between the input and output coordinates (Fig. 2).

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